

The Idaean syndrome

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6. Introduction

By analysing first-millennium Anatolian names containing the elements *ida-*, *id-*, *d-*, and *ila-*, this study argues that their distribution reflects a deep-rooted cultural “syndrome” linked to Mt. Ida and preserved in Greek myth. As the epigraphic and literary contexts of these names rarely provide unambiguous support, the hypothesis can gain structural strength only through a broad network of attested data. The investigation therefore broadens its scope without presupposing a fixed chronological depth for the “Idaean syndrome,” and without applying definitive linguistic criteria for isolating these elements within compound forms. In some cases, the phenomenon appears to have developed across cultural boundaries and historical periods — a cross-cultural diffusion that gains plausibility if the migrations of populations from Mysia towards south-eastern Anatolia are understood as historically grounded rather than purely mythographic. From this perspective, the evidence provided by onomastic clusters has also strengthened the expectation of finding corroborating archaeological evidence.

Although identifying evidence of the Idaean syndrome and Mysian migrations within the Hieroglyphic Luwian inscriptions of Tabal remains my primary focus, this inquiry invites a deeper chronological reach. Extending this framework into the Bronze Age enables exploration of potential roots within the Hittite imperial core — an avenue worth pursuing, however tentative the proposed correlations may appear.

6.1. *Labarna/Laparna*, namely “the house of La”?

Faced with one of the major vexed questions in Hittitology, a convenient — if inevitably partial — point of departure is what A. Kloekhorst (EDHIL 521) argues s.v. *labarna-*, *tabarna-*:

Already on the basis of these spelling peculiarities alone, I would conclude that *l/tabarna-* must be of non-IE origin (seemingly an adaptation of something like [t̪afarna-]). And if we are indeed dealing with an original personal name that only secondarily came to be used as the title of the Hittite kings, the original meaning cannot be determined. I therefore see no possible way to etymologize this word.

Kloekhorst’s entry already conveys how puzzling and contentious the matter is — a situation examined at length by I. Yakubovich (2002a) and M. Valério (2015), both of whom draw on E. Eichner (1975, 81 n. 5) in their discussions of *labarna-*:

Fremdwort bzw. Lehnwort aus einer idg. Sprache Anatoliens (idg. Eroberungen, also Herrschertitel ohne weiteres als idg. denkbar!), wahrscheinlich aus dem Dialekt der Gegend von Hattuša (die Form mit *l-* ist wohl weiter südlich beheimatet; König Labarna stammte nicht aus Hattuša; vgl. vielleicht auch lyk. PN Λαπάρας = Dapara TL 6, *p* abweichend).

Any attempt to shed new light on the etymological aspect of the matter would be presumptuous, given how authoritatively Oettinger (1994 316) and Melchert (2019 341 n. 50) have addressed the question. My aim is rather to offer a new perspective, possibly avoiding the tendency to descend into

obscurum per obscurius in the search for Anatolian comparative evidence. Yet what A. Archi (2015 6) rightly identifies may serve as the cornerstone for any subsequent line of inquiry, at least from a historical perspective: “The dynasty of Labarna I and Labarna II could only belong to a branch of the same family of Anitta, from Kussara.”¹ Although scholars debate whether *labarna-* began as a proper name or a title,² its firm historical correlates offer a secure foundation for analysis. Before reviewing that history, I will build upon this tentative proposal using a key observation by Unger (1959 14 n. 9):

Die “Blüte” hat den Lautwert “La” (Meriggi) 180). der sog. “Dolch” hat mit einem solchen keine Ähnlichkeit, eher mit einer Pinzette. Er ist nämlich bei dem Zeichen rechts auf der Ädikula genauer gezeichnet und zwar unten angespalten, also unten offen. Er macht eher den Eindruck einer Krebs— oder Skorpionsschere. Daß diese Aufspaltung Absicht ist. beweist das Siegel desselben Königs, wo beide Formen so gestaltet sind.

This brief annotation is original and suggestive, though it lacks the depth of Carruba and Mora’s (1990) or Hawkins’s (1995 108–113) treatment of the “sign *Labarna* (HH no. 277)” corresponding to Meriggi 289 (1937 91). The persistent difficulties in interpreting this sign are well-documented by Marazzi (1990 192):

A tutt’oggi l’interpretazione come titolo “tabarna” non soddisfa completamente. Per quanto riguarda l’uso del titolo cf. il recente studio di Mora 1988, p. 249ss. Per l’ipotesi che il segno, per quanto concerne la sua parte superiore, possa rappresentare una forma stilizzata di L. 371 (= IUSTITIA), cf. Hawkins apud Starke in RIA 6, s.v. *labarna*, p. 408. Una riconsiderazione globale del segno è ora offerta in Carruba-Mora 1990.

In proposing a comparison with L. 371, Hawkins’s post-1995 approach intentionally distanced itself from earlier interpretations such as “Dolch+Blüte” (Bossert 1944 236) or “POIGNARD(?) + la” (Laroche 1960 145–146). However, this shift highlights a persistent uncertainty. Hawkins himself openly acknowledged this vulnerability in 2021,³ and his 2024⁴ assessment confirms that the debate has essentially come full circle, returning the analysis to its original starting point (Hawkins 2024 400):

L.277. *LABARNA*. (Empire) Logogram+first syllable complement, +*la* (not “Dolch am Blute”, as originally identified); used as title on seals of Tudhaliya IV, Arnuwanda III, Suppiluliuma II, also Kuruntiya, and Labarna seals (now NIŞANTEPE 2, nos. 149–189). Earliest attestation: RN of early Hittite king Labarna on CRUCIFORM seal side i, upper (dated Mursili II?).

A possible way out of this impasse is to consider that L. 277 may refer to Hittite *lappa-* (Hoffner 2003 623), since this term likely means “fire tongs”:⁵

lappa-: The traditional translation “tongs” followed also in this case by the vastly to be preferred to “scoop, shovel.” Only a preconceived etymology leads Puhvel prefer his translation. The “remains” (Puhvel) that are transferred with the *lappa-* bones (*ḥaštai*). A scoop might be used for ashes, but *ḥaštai* means “bones,” while means “ashes.”

¹ Cf. R. Beal (2003); Simon (2020).

² Cf. CHD L-N 41-43; HEG I 34-41; HED Starke (1980–1983); Tischler (1988); Soysal (2005).

³ Hawkins (2021 799): “It is probably not — *contra* Hawkins, *StBoT* Bh. 3, pp. 108–113 — descended from L.277, *LABARNA*.”

⁴ Hawkins (2024 409): “L.371.I.1. IUSTITIA, “justice”. (Late) logogram, suggested as descended from Empire L.277 (*LABARNA*) (Hawkins, *StBoT* Bh. 3, pp. 108–113, Appendix 4); read traditionally *tarwana-*; but now Melchert argues for *tarrawann(i)-*. (*Fs Salvini*, pp. 337–345), which would exclude *LABARNA* derivation.”

⁵ HED L 60; CHD L-N 40, s.v. *lappa-*. Cf. Sommer (1939 681); Neumann (1969 225); Beckman (1983 17); Polvani (1995 158); Kassian, Sidel'tsev, and Korolëv (2002 283); Fincke (2004 226); García Ramón (2008 38); Michel (2014 200); Vigo (2014 31 and n. 61); Mouton (2020 25). *Contra* Marazzi (2020 305): “Die Identifizierung von ^(URUDU)*lappa-* (und seinen verschiedenen Erwähnungen in Edelmetall) mit der ‘fenestrated ax’ passt gut zu den archäologischen Daten und der Ikonographie, die sie repräsentiert.”

If we accept the comparison between the LABARNA sign and Unger’s “*Pinzette*,” a further step naturally follows: the sign may represent fire tongs.⁶ This tool could potentially anchor the symbol in the historical record of the period between 1650 and 1600 BC, traditionally associated with Labarna I. This convergence finds unexpected material support in the MBA findings from Akrotiri (Thera) (Michailidou 2021 280–281):

In situ metalworking is attested by the craftsman’s tools, such as hammer-stones found in second use in the settlement, crucibles, tuyères for blowpipes or bellows, which so far are found in the Aegean in pairs, and the bronze fire-tongs, which is the best preserved specimen of the so-called ‘Aegean’ type, as opposed to the Cypriot type.

Fig. 1a: Aegean fire tongs from Akrotiri⁷

The case becomes stronger still when we turn to the object’s material description by Michailidou (2008 246, Fig. V.29a–b) (our Fig. 1b):

Bronze tongs found in room Delta 18a of House Delta East and manufactured with care from a high tin copper alloy that gives them a gold colour. They are of the so called ‘Aegean type’ and are decorated with parallel grooves along the edges.

Fig. 1b (detail of fig. 1a)⁸

L 277, which “can be seen as a sign dividing at the bottom into two ‘legs’” (Hawkins 1995 109), may recall the form of a tool of a type attested in the Aegean during the Old Hittite period.

This “grooved” and “legged” character can be noticed when we compare the fire tongs from Akrotiri (figs. 1a-1b) with L 277 in the KARAKUYU inscription (fig. 2):⁹

⁶ Coghlan (1941 80): “How early the invention of the tongs was made is uncertain. Tweezers are tongs on a miniature scale, and it seems logical to think that the tongs may have developed from the tweezers, of the antiquity of which there is no doubt.”

⁷ By Olaf Tausch - Own work, CC BY 3.0, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=30018377>.

⁸ Michailidou (2008 246, Fig. V.29a–b).

⁹ Hawkins (2024 37–39).

Fig. 2¹⁰

K.Bittel - 1984

Perhaps even closer to L 277 is what Childe (1944 10) describes as the evolution of tweezers:

The smith's labour was lightened by a primitive sort of bellows and by the enlargement of tweezers into tongs capable of holding small objects (see Fig. 4).

His figure 4 is from the tomb of Rekh-mi-Rē at Thebes (TT 100), which Davies (1943) shows on Plate LIII, row 3 (our Fig. 3):¹¹

Fig. 3

The earliest secure attestation of this achievement in Egyptian metallurgy is conventionally placed in the New Kingdom (c. 1440–1420 BCE), though a possibly earlier, Middle Kingdom precedent has been proposed; the scenario is set out by Scheel (1989 56) as follows:

The earliest evidence for the use of tongs appears in metalworking scenes in the New Kingdom tomb of the Vizier Rekhmire (figure 31), or possibly earlier in the Middle Kingdom tomb of the nomarch Khety of the Twelfth Dynasty (figure 30). These lifting tongs were used to hold metal objects in position for annealing in a fireplace. Tongs with special forms of jaw to hold objects or well developed surgical forceps like those depicted in Kom Ombo were not known before the Roman Period.

An even clearer depiction (fig. 4) of fire tongs is found in TT 100 as well (Davies 1943 Plate LV, row 3):

¹⁰ <https://www.hittitemonuments.com/karakuyu/>

¹¹ Cf. Scheel (1989 32, fig. 31).

Fig. 4

Based on what Hawkins (1990 737) calls “antithetic LABARNA-signs” typical of Hittite royal seals and given that “277+la only appears in the Hier. titulary particularly but not exclusively in the aediculae” (Hawkins 1995 113), we must consider whether this sign carries a distinct symbolic value related to metallurgic tools. This iconographic inquiry aligns with a potential morphological analysis of the title *labarna/laparna*- itself as a compound of **la-* and **-parna-* (“house of La”). This etymological framework likely finds support in Anatolian onomastics. For instance, the toponym *Zišparna*¹² or the PN **Asulaparna*.¹³ Given that Hittite toponyms provide evidence of several names beginning with **zi(š)-*: *Ziṣhana*, *Ziškuliya*, *Ziṣpa*, *Ziṣpinuwa*, *Zištama*, *Ziṣparna* can be convincingly interpreted as “house/household of Zi(š).”

Extending this logic to royal iconography, the LABARNA-sign and the so-called “Labarna-seals”¹⁴ were probably intended to evoke a presumed “house of La.” If the element *La-* can in turn be connected to Mt. Ida, the resulting mountain motif establishes a conceptual bridge to the 13th-century BCE king Tudḫaliya IV.¹⁵ Not only was his name written with the logogram *MONS.tu*,¹⁶ but he also revived the use of the LABARNA-sign¹⁷ — a symbol absent from royal seals since its prominent

¹² RGTC VI/1 511-612; Cornelius (1958 229, 244; 1963 239, 241 n. 3); Singer (1984 115); Ünal (1984 107); Forlanini (1992 299 and n. 86); Haas (1994 776); Forlanini (2008 185 n. 109); Barjamovic (2011 254 n. 966); Forlanini (2012 295); Kryszewski (2016 127, 303, 357); Carnevale (2017–2018)

¹³ Mosca and Russell (1987); Lemaire (1989 124, 28 n. 7); Younger (2003); Röllig (2008); Freu and Mazoyer (2012 160); Matessi and Giusfredi (2025 55 n. 2). **Asulaparna* is probably the Anatolian PN rendered with the Phoenician ŠLPRN on the Cebelireis Dağı Inscription (1-2). Cf. Giusfredi (2024 32–33, 37), who does not take a stand on a possible Anatolian equivalent.

¹⁴ Herbordt, Bawanypeck, and Hawkins (2011 19, 32, 41–42). Cf. Herbordt (2006 97 n. 1): “Because the title ‘Labarna’ (IUDEX.LA) is found only in the seal and stone inscriptions of the last two generations of Hittite kings, Tuthaliya IV to Suppiluliuma II, we have a firm basis for dating the ‘Labarna’-seals (see Hawkins 1995, 108ff.; Otten 1967, 229 pp.).” Soysal (2011b 327) tries to account for the “singularity” of Labarna-seals as follows: “The issue of the New Hittite anonymous *labarna*-seals under Tuthaliya IV may have had an ideological link to the Old/Early–Middle Hittite anonymous *tabarna*-seal tradition, which aimed for a certain archaism in the royal-administrative sphere.”

¹⁵ Lombardi (1997 86–87): “Questa antica tradizione, che associa le montagne al concetto di regalità, tradizione profondamente radicata nella cultura nord-anatolica, di forte matrice hattica, sembra ricevere un nuovo impulso all’epoca di Tudḫaliya IV. La scelta stessa del nome dinastico, Tudḫaliya, che è notoriamente anche il nome di una montagna, presumibilmente della zona settentrionale, appare, in certo senso, programmatica. Non dimentichiamo che è dalla fine del Medio Regno che questo nome non era più stato utilizzato dai sovrani ittiti e che, nella scrittura geroglifica anatolica, Tudḫaliya è scritto con il pittogramma di montagna (L. 207).” Cf. Lombardi (1996).

¹⁶ Mouton (2016 1–2): “a logogram is sometimes followed, in the inscriptions, by a syllabic sign that gives the phonetic reading of the beginning of the word, like in *MONS.TU* that one can read ‘Mountain Tudḫaliya’. Personally, I wonder whether it would not be even more accurate to transcribe this as ^(MONS)tu, which would be an abbreviated form for the mountain’s name.”

¹⁷ Hawkins (1995 109): “The Hier. sign HH no. 277 is found in the titularies of the last two generations of the dynasty of Hattusa only, that is on seals and stone inscriptions of Tudḫaliya IV and his two sons Amuḫanda III and Suppiluliuma II, and also as recently discovered on seals of Tudḫaliya’s cousin, Kurunta, King of Tarḫuntassa.”

appearance on the Old Kingdom “Cruciform Seal” (A.M. Dinçol et al. 1993).¹⁸ This iconographic revival reflects the deeply rooted Hittite ideological triad linking sacred mountains, kingship, and iron metallurgy (Freu 2006 237):¹⁹

Le dieu-montagne possédait un principe vital dont les rois tiraient leur force. Il était en général représenté par une statuette de fer ou d’argent tenant souvent un croissant de lune et un disque solaire.

From this, it may be easier to address the problem described as unanswerable by Hawkins (1995 113):

Finally we return to the problem of why the title *277+*la* only appears in the Hier. titularies, particularly but not exclusively in the aediculae, of the last two generations of Hattusa. [...] we have seen that the cruciform seal, dated to the reign of Mursili II, attests the occurrence of *277+*la* as early as that period, though there used to write the name not the title. Also it has been observed that neither Suppiluliuma I nor Mursili II use the title *Tabarna* in their Cun. titularies. Muwatalli, Urhi-Tesub and Hattusili certainly did. The question thus reduces itself to an enquiry why the latter three kings did not use an equivalent of Cun. *Tabarna* in their Hier. titularies, and why it was only Tudhaliya IV and his successors that introduced the Hier. equivalent *277+*la*. In fact it must be admitted that there is no very obvious answer to this question.

My proposal is to explain the revival of the LABARNA-sign during Tudhaliya IV’s reign by noting that *labarna-* was etymologically linked to a place — Mt. Ida, famous for iron production. The religious reform initiated by this king (Laroche 1975) required replacing old cult statues with iron ones. Since the *labarna-* title itself carried this Idaean (and thus iron) association, and the Labarna-seals continued the ideological program of the Tabarna-seals,²⁰ the iron metaphor was central to the message they were meant to convey (Bilgin 2018 15–16):

Absolute powers of the kings are also more vividly demonstrated in the Old Hittite period. All of the known royal seals of the Hittite kings up to Muwatalli I include the statement “Seal of Tabarna, Great King; whoever alters (it) shall be put to death.” Most of these seals are known from their impressions on land donation texts. Almost all of these texts include the formulaic statement in their closing paragraphs: “The word of Tabarna, Great King, is made of iron. (It is) not to be discarded, not to be broken. Whoever alters (it), his head will be cut off.”

When Cordani (2016 166) notes that “in several OH and MH texts, as well as in their later copies, the king and his family play a central role” and “the early mentions of iron seem to indicate a strong relation between this metal and kingship,” she refers to the appearance of this metal “in symbolic and metaphorical passages, as in the land grants, where the word of *tabarna* is compared to iron,” or to “the Benedictions for Labarna, where the king is compared to ‘the iron of the Sun’” (Cordani 166 n. 21).

From this perspective, might the name Idari (NH 82, § 478)²¹ — borne by a “king of the mountain” who appears in the rite (IBoT 1.1) celebrated by Tudhaliya IV in honour of the mountain-god Piškuruwa — conceal a reference to Mt. Ida? At present, this must remain a passing insight, hypothetically permitted if Güterbock (1986 36) is correct in assuming that “Wilusa was brought under Hittite overlordship already under Labarnas, probably II, of the Old Kingdom (before 1600).”

¹⁸ Hawkins (1995 110): “[...] we have on it the earliest attestation of the sign *277+*la*, not found elsewhere until the reign of Tudhaliya IV.”

¹⁹ Cf. Gonnet (1968); Haas (1982); Siegelová (1984 109–113).

²⁰ Easton (1981).

²¹ Laroche records *I-d[a]-ri-iš* in Old Assyrian cuneiform texts (TCL XX191, 7). Cf. NH 312 n. 42; Gonnet (1968 133); Haas (1982 46, 59–60; 1994 183, 820); Lombardi (1997 106 and n. 91, 107–109); Trabazo (2009 78); Galmarini (2013 344 n. 39); Malerba (2023–2024 74).

6.2. Leleges and Idaeans

If we take the irregular Lydian sound change $*-t- > -l-$,²² we can go one step further and segment *Λέλεγες* as follows: $*Lele-$ + $*-ges$,²³ where the first element can be interpreted as $*Lele-$ < $*Dele-$ < $Ida-$ + $-le$. Apart from the initial $-l-$ instead of $*-t-$, which occurs as an irregular change in Lydian, but also in Luwian and Lycian,²⁴ the suffix $-le/i$ is typical of the latter language. We must therefore question whether a Lycian origin of the ethnonym can be maintained. What Valério (2015 341) writes about “the Lycian personal name *Dapara* — which is rendered as *Λαπαρας* in Greek in a Lycian bilingual inscription from Karmylesson (TL 6)”²⁵ — is a decisive step towards understanding its etymology:²⁶

Two points that usually go unmentioned in discussions of *Dapara* are: 1) Lycian avoids word-initial $d-$; 2) when words beginning with geminate dd follow a copulative se , the two fuse and de-gemination takes place: cf. $ddewē > se=dewē$ (see Melchert 2004: 9). *Dapara* too follows a copulative, $se=dapara$ (ibid.: 92), so its actual self-standing form must be $*Ddapara$. This has implications for the etymology and pronunciation of the name. There is the possibility that Lyc. $ddV-$ reflects earlier $*VdV$, and therefore I would like to suggest as a working hypothesis that $*Ddapara$ contains *Ida*, a fairly common Luwic formant of names that appears in Hellenized transcriptions as $Iδ(α)-/Eιδ(α)$. This suggestion finds a degree of support in Myl. *Ddxug[a]*, which, despite being damaged, invites a comparison with Car. *dquq* and Greek written *Ιδαγυγος* (as proposed tentatively by Adiego 1995: 27, n. 9). Notice that the segmentation of the Carian name as *dquq* is independently supported by the existence of *quq* as a self-standing name. The term of comparison is the abovementioned Lyc. *Idazzala > Eιδα-σσαλα*, alongside *Zzala > Σαλας* (see Adiego 2007: 334). If this proposition is correct, what we have is $*Idapara > Ddapara$, with the same kind of (accent-driven?) aphaeresis seen in Mylian and Carian. Given the Lycian avoidance of initial d , we would expect this consonant to undergo gemination after aphaeresis in order to keep up with the phonotactic demands of the language (Van den Hout 1995: 135). Irrespective of the etymology of $(se=)dapara$, it seems that the $λ$ of *Λαπαρας* renders the “simple” intervocalic d , possibly owing to circumstances like those of *Xesntedi > Κεσινδηλις* (if the latter is not the result of dissimilation).

Based on the above premises, Lycian PNN such as *Δελεπιμις* (KPN 145, § 265-1)²⁷ and *Δελεπιας* (KPN 145, § 265-2)²⁸ raise doubts about their correct interpretation. However, the Lydian GN *Κομβδιλιπια* (KON 282, § 566) and *Τανδου* (KON 598-599, § 1292),²⁹ villages near Sardis,³⁰ can offer support. These GNN occur in the so-called “Mnesimachos inscription” (3rd century BC)³¹ Since *Δελεπιμις* and *Τανδάσις*³² appear in the same inscription from Bayındır (Antiphellos) and are only attested in Lycia, it stands to reason that *Κομβδιλιπια* can be explained as evidence of a migration of Lycians, perhaps craftsmen from *Komba*,³³ which is revered as their homeland and as $*διλιπια$,

²² LW II 22: “Ein Wechsel t/l begegnet in *antola/anlola* (LW), ferner vielleicht in *silavad* neben *fa-sitavad*. Zu beachten ist ferner die Wiedergabe eines fremden Dentals durch l im Anlaut von *levs* und *lamētruś*.”

²³ For some tentative proposals about $*-ges$, see Papi (2024b).

²⁴ Valério (2015 331): “The lambdacist transcription of *Dapara* as Grk. *Λαπαρας* would reflect this alien $/d/$.”

²⁵ Schürr (1996 154).

²⁶ Cf. Adiego (2020 51): “Encontramos la correspondencia licio $d <d>$: griego $λ$ en los nombres indigenas *xesntedi > Κεσινδηλις* (bil.) *dapara > Λαπαρας* (bil.). En el caso de *xesntedi > Κεσινδηλις* ya hemos comentado la posibilidad de que se trate de un nombre cario. En el segundo caso también tenemos documentada en la epigrafía griega la forma con $δ$ (*Δαπαρας*). Esta alternancia así como el hecho excepcional de que en licio el nombre empiece por $d-$ simple (apenas hay algún otro ejemplo seguro) me lleva a pensar que también pueda tratarse de un nombre no específicamente licio.”

²⁷ Schwyer (2002 232).

²⁸ LGPN VB 98. Cf. Baker and Thériault (2023 104 n. 11).

²⁹ Buckler and Robinson (1912 48–49).

³⁰ Buckler and Robinson (1932 3, 6); Atkinson (1972 47, 69–70).

³¹ Debord (1982 244–251); Hanfmann (1983 13–14); Descat (1985); Billows (1995 137–145); Roosevelt (2003 208; 2019 152–154); Yegül (2024).

³² KPN 484, § 1502; LGPN VB 400. Cf. the Mysian GN *Ταδοκωμη* (KON 595, § 1278).

³³ Buckler and Robinson (1912 44–45); Cuny (1913 402).

namely “gift of Ida,”³⁴ suggesting that they were smiths.³⁵ If Τανδάσις ≈ Τενδεσσιος (“of Tenedos?”),³⁶ we would have confirmed the connection with Mysia, but also with Boiotia, which was involved in the colonisation of the island (Tufano 2023 44–48).

Since the two villages mentioned above lie within Τοβαλμουρα (KON 625, § 1348), it is worth recalling that Τοβαλοας is a Lycian theonym³⁷ that can now be understood as **tuwal-* + *-uwa*, i.e. “of **Tuwal-*,” possibly the Anatolian avatar of Dionysos, as argued in an earlier section. Τοβαλμουρα can then be parsed as **tuwal-* + **moura*, the latter going back to the root **mur-* which Poetto (1993) recognised in HLUw. *mu-ru-wa-tà-za*.³⁸

The Lydian toponym could thus be a compound in which the second element is a cognate of CLuw. *mur(i)-* “cluster of grapes (?)” (Sasseville and Höfler 2025),³⁹ while the first occurs in the Lycian PN *Tuwala* (TL 42b).⁴⁰ Based on these considerations, from which Lycian features have emerged, we can derive a confirmation of the above hypothesis that Τοβαλμουρα and its villages were a settlement of Lycian craftsmen. Moreover, the mention of Mt. Ilos (KON 197, § 370-2) or the village of Ilos in the Mnesimachos inscription could further strengthen this conviction, for Ἴλιος again refers to Mysia, to the Idaean *goētes*, known as the ancestors of the metallurgists (Chiai 2017 64), and the combination with **-dilipia* “gift of Ida” recognised in Κομβδιλιπια would complete the evidence.

If Τοβαλμουρα is the flag of Lycian emigrants, we can go even further and assume that it means “grapes of Tuwa-(=Dionysos).” following Sasseville (2021 178 n. 12), who proposes Myra as “the town of grapes.”

As a tentative conclusion, I would suggest that Λαπαρας for **Idapara* > *Ddapara* was only an occasional but punctual rendering of the Lycian *d* in Greek transmission, while in the case of Δελεπιμυς and Δελεπιας the Greek delta stood for the initial *dd-* which was typical of the Lycian epichoric orthography.⁴¹

6.3. Is there such a place as La-la Land?

The mid-9th century CLuwian inscription of MARAŞ 4 (§ 4-6, CHLI 255-258)⁴² mentions the conquest of the towns of Hirika and Iluwasi by Halparuntiya, king of Gurgum. Regarding Iluwasi M. Weeden (2023)⁴³ has recently restated the localisation suggested by D. Hawkins⁴⁴ though he added a new interesting element:

It has been suggested that Hirika might refer to Hilakku (Rough Cilicia), and a newly discovered inscription from the end of the tenth century BC reports Gurgum taking action against Adana and Hilika, which would seem to support this identification.

³⁴ Zgusta (1964a 93–102); Cf. Réveilhac (2024 86–87). Cf. Δαλιοσαλλος (LGPN VB 94).

³⁵ Cf. Papi (2024a).

³⁶ KPN 509, § 1534; Blümel (1992–2012 23; 1993).

³⁷ Adiego (2015 409); Schürr (2016a 32).

³⁸ Cf. Weiss (1996).

³⁹ Cf. DLL 122; Melchert (2003a 136 n. 10); Schürr (2016b 165); Sasseville (2021 177–178).

⁴⁰ Cf. Adiego (2014).

⁴¹ Van den Hout (1995 135): “Note that word-initial **#b-* and **#d-* do not exist at all, only *#dd-* where the gemination can only be explained, it seems, out of a phonetic reluctance to start a word with a (voiced) fricative. The onset of the word caused a fortition which finds its graphic expression in the geminate.”

⁴² Morpurgo Davies (1986 139); Yakubovich (2002 203); Ponchia (2006 211); Goedegebuure (2010 82); Serangeli (2015 171); Goedegebuure (2019 305); Hawkins (2024 224).

⁴³ Cf. Matessi and Giusfredi (2025 65): “However, suggested comparisons of both toponyms with Hilakku, the Assyrian name of Rough Cilicia, may be more persuasive depending on the reading of Muwizi’s inscription (MARAŞ 17), where Hiliki reportedly appears coupled with Adana.”

⁴⁴ CHLI 251: “The text as preserved describes mainly his conquest of two places, the city (also land) of Hirika and the city Iluwasi, and his accession to the throne, at which point it breaks off. Hirika could be identified with the city Hiliki mentioned on a MALATYA inscription from Elbistan, and the place might be sought as a border territory between Gurgum and the plain of Elbistan, although a connection with the distant Hilakku (Rough Cilicia) has been suggested”.

He thus refers to MARAŞ 17 (Denizhanoğulları, Gürüçin, and Peker 2018 60),⁴⁵ where Hirika and Adana are mentioned together, supporting the view that Cilicia is at issue. However, I now wish to focus on *Iluwasi*, a hapax that bears a striking resemblance to *Wiluša*⁴⁶ and to what has long been considered its linguistic precursor (Güterbock 1986 35):⁴⁷

Sommer, with all due disclaimers that this was not his opinion but only a possible “way out” for those who insist on the equation of Wilusa with Ilios, suggested that in addition to the initial digamma one might assume a form *Wiluwa “without the -s- suffix”: *Wiluas > Wilios.

Even setting aside the linguistic equivalence between Greek Ἰλιος and Hittite *Wiluša*,⁴⁸ independent grounds exist for tracing Mysian influence in Gurgum (the Neo-Assyrian Marqasi)⁴⁹. Indeed, the toponym *Marqasi* itself offers perhaps the most suggestive evidence for this broader historical connection. Parsed as the Luwian possessive adjective **marqa-asi*, its first element strongly recalls Μάρκαιον (TIB XIII 757),⁵⁰ a mountain in the Troad near Gergis, and closely mirrors the ethnonym Μαρκαίισσιοι (SB III 269, § 73). Furthermore, the *Markaioi* listed in the Athenian tribute lists⁵¹ may be directly reflected in *markasi-*. Viewed as a substantivized, *i*-mutated Hieroglyphic Luwian possessive adjective⁵² used to denote ethnic affiliation, *markasi-* would precisely translate to “of Marka.”

Even more striking consequences can be drawn from a new perspective on *Astuwalamanza/Astuwaramanza*,⁵³ two versions of a royal name found in the KARKAMIŞ⁵⁴ and MARAŞ HLuw. inscriptions.⁵⁵ If we parse it as **astuwara-* + *-maza-* (“Maza of Astyra”),⁵⁶ we find two known elements. The first corresponds to *Astyra*, a well-known Mysian toponym,⁵⁷ and the second to *Maza-*, attested in the PN *Maza-Karhuḫa* from the Ankara silver bowl (ANKARA 2),⁵⁸ but which could also refer to Mysia again, specifically near Pergamon, where a GN Μασδυη or Μαζυη (KON 372, § 784) is known.

⁴⁵ Hawkins (2024 130).

⁴⁶ RGTC VI/1 484-485; VI/2 189.

⁴⁷ Cf. Röllig (1992 194); Neumann (1999 21 and n. 20).

⁴⁸ Hajnal (2003 29–32, 42).

⁴⁹ RGTC VII/1 169-170; Parpola (1970 239–240); Jiménez, Adalı, and Radner (2015 154): “The local Luwian inscriptions call the country “(city of) Gurgum” (*kurkuma*-(URBS)): the city name Marqasi is only attested in Assyrian sources from the time of Šarru-ukīn II (r. 721–705 BCE) onwards.”

⁵⁰ KON 230 n. 232. Refer to Kiepert (1909 11) for a map of the area including the mountain. Cf. Cook (1973 286–287); Foss et al. (2021).

⁵¹ IACP 113 and n. 19: “In addition to all the allies recorded by city-ethnic and/or toponym there are in the lists [...] three communities recorded by an ethnic which may be a city-ethnic denoting a polis but may also have been a regional ethnic denoting a people: the Maiandrioi, the Markaioi, and the Mysoi.”

⁵² Payne (2010 80).

⁵³ Goedegebuure (2010 77): “The name *Astuwaramanza-* is therefore derived from *Astuwalamanza-*.”

⁵⁴ Simon (2014b 721–722): “[...] it was proposed that this *Astuwalamanza* is identical to the REGIO.DOMINUS of Karkamiš of the same name (cf. Hawkins 2002: 58). Though the exact date of *Astuwalamanza* of Karkamiš is not known, there are good arguments for 10th c. (Hawkins 2000: 5), thus approximately end of 10th c. / beginning of 9th c. for Larama.”

⁵⁵ Hawkins (2024 641).

⁵⁶ Kloekhorst (2004 39 n. 26): “This name, which is to be analysed as *ás-tu* + *áta_{4/5}-manza-* (lit. ‘let it be (his) name’), shows a genuine allography between *ta_{4/5}* and *la* in the word for ‘name’. The one attestation *á-sa-tu-¹wa/i¹-ra/i-ma-za-* (MARAŞ § 8 § 1), however, would be an argument in favour of an interpretation [adamanza] as it seems to show rhotacism from intervocalic -d-. Nevertheless, the occurrence of rhotacism in such an early inscription is problematic (cf. Hawkins 2002: 253).”

⁵⁷ For Astyra near Abydos and thus near Markaion, or at least its supposed location, cf. TIB XIII 433, s.v. *Astyra*.

⁵⁸ Hawkins (2024 87–90). Cf. Mora (2007); Simon (2009); Durnford (2010); Rotislav Oreshko (2012); Giusfredi (2013); Weeden (2013a 7–8); Payne (2015 84–97); d’Alfonso and Cohen (2021); Warbinek (2023).

The choice between an interpretation favouring Emar⁵⁹ — where King Maziya is known from a letter from Talmi-Šarruma to the governor of Suḫu (Cohen 2015 175)⁶⁰ — and one favouring Mysia may currently depend on the well-known genealogy of the Gurgumite kings.⁶¹ There, several kings named *Larama* (ISKENDERUN, MARAŞ 1; 8; 16; 17) are found, probably to be compared with other HLuw. names such as *La*,⁶² *Lali*⁶³ and *Lara*(?).⁶⁴ From the KÜRTÜL (§ 1) inscription⁶⁵ we learn that *La* is the son of *Lara*(?),⁶⁶ suggesting that the latter's name is derived from *La* by means of the adjectival suffix *-ra/i-*.⁶⁷

To appreciate how far-reaching and ancient a possible link with Mysia and Mt. Ida may be, an intriguing — if daring — angle is offered by the song of Zababa, a warrior god, which Lariya and his sons are said to sing according to the “Siege of Uršu” (CTH 7).⁶⁸ Below are the respective interpretations of this difficult passage by G. M. Beckman⁶⁹ and Th. van den Hout.⁷⁰

The sons of Lariya, and Lariya (himself), while inactive, sang the song (of² the War-god) Zababa “We have *clogged*² the threshing-floor with *lahni*! The puppies were wearing helmets²!”

The sons of I.ariya (and) Lariya are marching (singing the song of the war god Zababa): “As helmet wearing(?) puppies we have pissed(?) on the threshing floor with *lahna/i*.”

This suggests that by the reign of Ḫattušili I (c. 1650 BC), Hittite contact with north-western Anatolia was established enough to integrate Mysians into the military. This is supported by CTH 7,

⁵⁹ de Martino (2016 114–115): “Questa coppa e l’iscrizione sono stati oggetti di molti studi e vengono datati ad epoche diverse, o nel pieno dell’età ittita (al tempo del re Tuthaliya I), oppure, come sembra molto più probabile, nel XII secolo. Zs. Simon ha proposto di riconoscere in Tuthaliya un re ittita successore di Suppiluliuma II, mentre Maza-Karhuha potrebbe essere un sovrano di Karkemish. Appare, però, più verosimile ritenere che Tuthaliya sia il re di uno stato siriano, forse dello stesso regno di Karkemish. Come C. Mora (2007b, 519) ha rilevato, il paese di Tarwiza potrebbe essere messo in relazione con la gente di Tarwa, menzionata come nemici di Emar nelle tavolette dell’ultima fase di vita di questa città. Si potrebbe avanzare l’ipotesi che Karkemish (se identifichiamo Tuthaliya come un re di questo paese) e un centro ad esso subordinato o alleato, quello retto da Maza-Karhuha, possano aver giocato un qualche ruolo negli scontri militari che portarono alla caduta di Emar (Weeden 2013, 7-8).”

⁶⁰ Cohen (2015 179): “One can imagine that at this point Maziya — a local Emarite — was installed as king by the new rulers of the Emar.” Cf. d’Alfonso and Cohen (2021).

⁶¹ Denizhanoğulları, Gürçin, and Peker (2018); Peker (2022).

⁶² Hawkins (2024 650).

⁶³ Hawkins (2024 650). Cf. Mysian *Lala*^f (KPN 265-266, § 790-1) and *Lalos* (KPN 266, § 790-3).

⁶⁴ Hawkins (2024 651).

⁶⁵ The Kürtül Stele was discovered near İsmaili village, approximately 8 kilometres southwest of Kürtül and 21 kilometres northwest (as the crow flies) of the central Citadel of Kahramanmaraş, the ancient capital of Gurgum. This location is geographically significant for comparison with other stelae such as the Stele of Laramas I (MARAŞ 4) found within the city of Maraş (modern-day Kahramanmaraş).

⁶⁶ CHLI 272: “(-)la+ra/i+a-sa: probably best taken as patronym, thus ‘Las (son) of Laras’ (the name naturally recalls the name *Laramas*, recurring at Gurgum, to the extent of implying a restoration {-ma-}. Alternatively it could be that *la-sá-la-ra/i* + *a-sa* is to be taken as a single name, *Laslaras*.” Cf. BoHa 19.203 for *Lara* and Soysal (2011a 331): “*Lara* (no. 203): If the reading of this name as *La+ra/i-á* is correct, one may not exclude the alter-native reading *La+ri-á* that matches exactly the cuneiform attestation *Lariya* (NH no. 690 [masc.]); cf. M. Poetto and S. Salvatori, *StMed* 3 (1981): 23, n. 32. The gender of *La+ra/i-á* may be female (see here Herbordt, p. 149 and Hawkins, p. 262), someone using the sign SCRIBA on her seal, thus indicating an educated woman rather than a female scribe; see also the remarks on p. 75 (with n. 576).” For *Lara/i(n)za/i*, BoHa 22.196-197. *Lariya* is another well-known Hittite PN, Easton (1981 24); Klengel (1998 97, 99); (Bilgin 2018 103–104).

⁶⁷ Hutter-Braunsar (2006 108): “So bezeichnet sich in der Inschrift KÜRTÜL ein gewisser Las, Sohn des Laras, ebenfalls als ‘Diener Tarhunzas’. Wohl wegen des Fehlens jeglicher Titel bezeichnet Hawkins (2000, 272) den Autor als ‘private citizen’. Demnach dürfte die Bezeichnung (DEUS) TONITRUS-*hu-ti-sá* SERVUS-*tas-ti-sá* zumindest in Maraş nicht als ein Element der Herrscherlegitimation gedeutet werden.”

⁶⁸ Güterbock (1938 113–139); Hoffner (1980 299–300); Haas (2006 45); Weeden (2013b 83–86).

⁶⁹ Beckman (1995 26).

⁷⁰ Van den Hout (2020 66).

where Lariya is paired with Šanta;⁷¹ since the latter — the likely field commander⁷² — bears a typical Luwian name, both men may have been from the north-west, if not from Mysia itself.

This need not seem surprising. In the “Tawagalawa letter” (AhT 4), a Hittite king — presumably Ḫattušili III (c. 1267–1237) — writes to an anonymous Ahḫiyawan ruler regarding Tapala-Tarhunta. As this royal charioteer was related to the queen and served both the king and Tawagalawa (Blackwell 2021 206), the same author infers close contact between high-ranking Hittite officers and Ahḫiyawan dignitaries (213):

This interaction between Hittite and Ahhiyawan officials must have occurred before the letter’s composition. It is difficult to imagine a scenario other than state-sponsored events where a royal Hittite charioteer would have driven Tawagalawa regularly. Diplomatic meetings between the Hittite king and Tawagalawa provided opportunities for such encounters. If Tawagalawa were the predecessor to the present Ahhiyawan king, these lines would refer to specific instances of royal contact, presumably in Anatolia.

Regarding two other figures mentioned in the “Siege of Uršu,” one, Menaniya (NH § 801),⁷³ has a name that M. Forlanini (2009 58, 62) considers to be of Assyrian origin, while the other’s name, Šariwanda (NH § 1120),⁷⁴ can usefully be compared to the Mysian *Sariandēs* (KPN 456, § 1375-1) attested at Pergamon.⁷⁵

Now, if we consider what in CTH 7 comes next the so-called “Song of Zababa”, we find a curious performance in which soldiers handle typically female objects, which Haas (2006 45) comments on as follows:⁷⁶

Das “Lied Zababa” begleitet einen an Santa vollzogenen Schandstrafenritus: Weibliche Attribute sollen die Feigheit (“die Schwäche der Frau”) des Generals Santa brandmarken, ihn (wahrscheinlich) vor dem Heer der Lächerlichkeit preisgeben und vor aller Augen mit Impotenz schlagen. Dem Inhalt des Liedes zufolge verläuft der Strafvollzug so, daß man martialische mit weiblichen Geräten bzw. Attributen vertauscht.

This scene can be compared to a Hittite rite involving the “men of Maša,”⁷⁷ summarised as follows by Arroyo (2020 35–36):

In a local cult text (KUB 17.35 (CTH 525.2) rev. iii 9–15), young men were divided into two groups, one with bronze weapons representing the men of Ḫattuša (LÚ^{MES} URU^{URU}GIDRU-*TI*), the other with reed weapons, the men of Maša (LÚ^{MES} URU^{URU}*Ma-a-ša*). After victory, the men of Ḫatti took a prisoner and brought him to the deity.

Maša is a region that some scholars consider the Hittite equivalent of Mysia⁷⁸ and although we cannot be certain about its location or this equivalence, some connections with other nearby regions

⁷¹ Cf. Dardano (1987 37, 89–90); R. Beal (2003 27); Forlanini (2009 62): “Šanda: not mentioned as far as I know in the old Assyrian texts, this personal name comes from that of the Luwian god, later identified with Marduk. He has been identified to a Šanda mentioned in the ‘Palace Chronicle.’” However, M. Forlanini (62 n. 59) shares P. Dardano’s doubt as to the latter is the same person who appears as commander in CTH 7. Cf. Forlanini (2010 118 n. 20). Haas (2006 42) seems to posit the identity of the two: “Santa scheint der oberste Befehlshaber der hethitischen Truppen zu sein. Er begegnet auch in der Exempelsammlung, wo er zur Strafe wegen seiner Feigheit vor den hurritischen Truppen verstümmelt worden ist.”

⁷² R.H. Beal (1992 362, 453–454).

⁷³ Cf. Manana, father of the Walastinean king Suppiluliuma (I) (Hawkins 2024 107, 139, 140ff., 651).

⁷⁴ Cf. BoHa 19.383; Flaata (2012 105 n. 309): “Lydian *Muattes* and *Sariandes* are linked to the Hittite names *Muwatti* and *Sariwanda*.”

⁷⁵ NI 124, 220.

⁷⁶ Cf. Weeden (2013b 84–85).

⁷⁷ Cf. Watkins (1995 338ff.).

⁷⁸ Strobel (2008 28): “Die Lokalisierung des Landes Masa ist bis heute umstritten, jedoch erhielt ein Ansatz im nordwestlichen Anatolien zunehmend Akzeptanz.” “Es ist festzuhalten, dass das Land Maša sich als geographischer Begriff offensichtlich mit der Zeit veränderte und eine ausgelernte Region nördlich von Ḫapalla und Seḫa sowie östlich von Wiluša bezeichnen konnte. Der Raum entspricht in etwa dem späterem Hellepontischen Phrygien und großen Teilen Mysiens” (29). Cf. Kelder (2004 87): “The province of Masa, finally, is for its mention in Linear B likely to be situated

in northwestern Anatolia are established. One of them is with Mira-Kuwaliya,⁷⁹ of which we know one ruler, *Mazlawā*, mentioned in the “Indictment of Madduwatta.” This PN can be interpreted as *Maza-* + *-lawā-*, that is “Maza of La” As noted at the beginning of this introduction, the king of Gurgum conquered Hirika and Iluwasi, and if we assume that the latter toponym was an avatar of *Wiluša*, we arrive at the hypothesis that Gurgum was somehow related to Mysia/Maša. At this point, it is significant to recall that in Hittite times Maša probably bordered Wiluša.⁸⁰

The geographic proximity of the KÜRTÜL and MARAŞ inscriptions suggests they originate from the same cultural milieu within the kingdom of Gurgum,⁸¹ where the MARAŞ texts identify Astuwaramanza as the dynastic founder. A Mysian origin for this lineage is plausible if one links the ancestor’s name to Astyra and identifies the onomastic stem **la-* as an avatar of Ida. This linguistic connection becomes evident when comparing the name of Larama III (son of Hunita),⁸² the predecessor of king Tarhulara (attested only in Assyrian records).⁸³

This ruler’s name — as well as that of his successor — aligns with the Gurgum tradition when parsed as *Tarhu-* + *-lara*.⁸⁴ By isolating **-lara* in these specific royal names, the hypothesised link between the Gurgum dynasty and Mysian Ida is further reinforced, considering that the above-cited HLuw. *Lala-* and *Lara-* may simply be variants and form part of the name of the well-known inhabitants of Ida’s foothills, namely the Leleges.

The element *Lala-/Lara-* likely functions as a “postnominal genitive adjective,”⁸⁵ a classification supported by personal names such as *Kunilara* (BoHa 19.177), when compared with *Kuni(ya)piya* (CTH 294) and *Kuniziti* or *Kuniyaziti* (NH 631).⁸⁶ According to a second millennium naming pattern (NP 10), **Kuni(ya)-* in the latter could represent a deity, which aligns with the LBA PN *Kuni(ya)lara* and the DN *Kunyawanna/i* (CTH 105)⁸⁷ — cases in which **-lara-* appears to qualify **Kuni(ya)-*, a Luwian theonym better understood by comparison with HLuw. *Mudiyawan(ni)-*, i.e. “of Mudi,” a

along the coast and to be identified with classical Mysia, in between the Troad and Lydia, the Iron Age successor of Late Bronze Age Mira.”

⁷⁹ Gander (2017 270): “Furthermore, one can say that Mira was not too far from Sallapa and finally that it is probable that Mira was rather close to Masa.”

⁸⁰ Gander (2017 272): “The land of Wilusa most probably bordered the land of Masa, since Muwatalli defeated this land on behalf of the Wilusan king Alaksandu, as is evident from the so-called Alaksandu treaty.” Hawkins (2019 351–352): “For Masa itself however there is an indication that it was close to Wilusa, namely Al, § 6, as restored, Beckman, § 4, where Muwatalli claims to have destroyed Masa in response to an appeal from Alaksandu. Its location is drawn towards north-western Anatolia by the report of its raids together with Kammala on Kassiya and the Hulana River lands, punished by Tudhaliya III acting with Suppiluliuma (DS frag. 13, E i 7–14) since Kassiya and the Hulana river later formed part of Hattusili’s north-western command along with Tummanna, Pala, Durmitta, etc. (Hatt ii 56–61).”

⁸¹ Matessi and Giusfredi (2025 64): “the reign of Astuwalamanza, forefather of the Gurgumean dynastic line, can be dated to around the late 11th century BCE.” Cf. Lovejoy (2023 78): “The kingdom of Gurgum also appears to have been founded during the late 11th century BCE, with its earliest preserved inscriptions, commissioned by Larama I, dating to the middle of the 10th century BCE and recounting two earlier generations of rulers in the initial genealogy, his father Muwatalli I and grandfather Astuwaramanza (MARAŞ 8). A late 10th century BCE inscription of Larama’s successor and son, Muwizi, records the same genealogy extended to include all four rulers (MARAŞ 17). In both inscriptions, no titles were applied to any.”

⁸² Denizhanoğulları, Gürüçin, and Peker (2018 60).

⁸³ Bagg (2011 213–214, 240 and n. 296). Cf. Gadd (1954 183) for an account of Sargon II’s punishment of Tarhulara for feuding with Mita of Muski. Cf. Matessi and Giusfredi (2025 64): “The last attested Gurgumean rulers are Tarhulara and his son Mutallu (i.e., Muwattalli), known only from the Assyrian records as contemporaries of Tiglathpileser III and Sargon II.”

⁸⁴ Cf. Simon (2014a 881 n. 18): “Tarhulara kann regelmäÙig aus **Tarhun-alla-* (mit luw. Rhotazismus) [Tarhurara-] erklärt werden.” Cf. Simon (2018 118) and Haas (2003 14 n. 72); Taracha (2009 67–68) on a putative *tarhunalla-*, regarding which HEG III 170 advises caution.

⁸⁵ Cf. the title “Tarhunza of the Vineyard” found in the mid-8th century BC SULTANHAN inscription (§2) (Bauer 2014 256) and the cases of “genitive relational adjective” such as ^dU *pihaššašiš*, “Storm god of lightning” (CTH 381 1, 41) and ^dU *hulaššašiš* “Storm god of Hulašša” (CTH 381 3, 4) (Lühr 2019 170).

⁸⁶ Imparati (2004 775 and n. 19).

⁸⁷ Beckman, Bryce, and Cline (2011 65). Cf. Gessel (1998–2001 262).

mountain mentioned in the 8th-century inscription BULGARMADEN.⁸⁸ As with the alternation *Wiluša/Wilušiya*,⁸⁹ moreover, the basic form of the GN proves equivalent to the suffixed one.

Following Neumann's 1976 232)⁹⁰ identification of the GN **Kuni-* as a component of *Kuniyawanna/i*, we can interpret the latter as “the one of Kuni” via the Luwian suffix *-wanna/i-*,⁹¹ which “is especially productive in forming adjectives from names for places” (Melchert 2003b 198–199).

Given that *Kuniyawanna/i* is the god of Lanta and the toponym itself represents an adjective in */-nt(i)-/* derived from **La-* (i.e., *Ida*) that was later substantivised, the element *-lara-* in both *Kunilara* and *Tarhulara* may function as an epiclesis common to Kuni(ya) and the Storm-god Tarhunt. This interpretation, however, faces a significant obstacle: understanding *-lara-* as a relational adjective meaning “Idaeon” is difficult to reconcile with *Lalanta*⁹² and *Lanta*,⁹³ two toponyms whose attested locations lie well outside the sphere of Mt. Ida.

This problem concerns the Anatolian extension of a phenomenon currently based on little more than onomastics. A solution requires demonstrating that the so-called “Idaeon syndrome” was already present during Hittite times, and ideally identifying the channels of its diffusion. To gain further insight into this linguistic connection, one may note that *Kunilara* is interpretable as “Kuni(ya) of La” — perhaps, “Kuni(ya) of Ida” — and that this is corroborated by two data points: Kukunni's

⁸⁸ CHLI 521ff.; Hawkins (1969 104–105; 1971 128); Yakubovich (2016 479); Hawkins (2024 282, 392); Santini (2024 27–29).

⁸⁹ Watkins (1986 35): “As for *Wilusiya*, the additional *-iya* is no obstacle to the identification with *Wilusa*, since there are other Anatolian place names that occur with and without this augment.” Cf. Rostislav Oreshko (2019 29 n. 37): “Doublets of the *Wilusa-Wilusiya* type are quite common. Houwink ten Cate lists the following examples: *Huwalusa - Huwalusiya*, *Arzawa - Arzawiya*, *Hulassa - Hulassiya*, *Marassanta - Marassantiya*, *Sananta - Sanantiya*, *Zithara - Zithariya* (JNES, 25 (1966), p. 186). It may be that *Wilusiya* designated a city, and *Wilusa* the surrounding country (a suggestion made to me by Professor Houwink ten Cate).”

⁹⁰ “Der Gottesname *Kuniyawanni-* ist eine luwische Ethnikonbildung, er weist also auf einen Ortsnamen **Kuni* zurück.”

⁹¹ Hutter (1988): “Durch die Namensbildung auf *-wanni* kann dieser Gott als luwisch betrachtet werden das Geschlecht des Gottes steht dabei nicht eindeutig fest, da IBoT III 123 I 1f das Epitheton GAŠAN-YA ‘meine Herrin’ der Gottheit zuordnet.”

⁹² RGTC V/1 240-241. Often associated with *Λαλανδος* in Phrygia (KON 327, § 679-1; TIB IV 170). Cf. Forlanini (1996 9 n. 25); Drew-Bear et al. (2024). *Contra* Hawkins (2019 356): “Starke following GG (p. 99 f.) identifies *Lalanda* with classical *Lalandos* just west of Amorium, and thus places *Hapalla* to the west of this. Since I doubt that Lower Land extended so far to the north-west into territory which I would identify as *Pedassa*, I prefer Garstang's original identification of *Lalanda* with *Laranda* (Karaman) and *Hapalla* to the west of this in *Pisidia*.” Recently Gander (2022 60–65) has taken up the entire dossier on Hittite *Lalanda*.

⁹³ Lebrun (2011 217): “La ville de Landa a fait l'objet de divers commentaires quant à sa situation géographique. Landa serait la ville de Karaman au Centre-Sud de l'Anatolie, au Nord de Mersin (cf. carte). Karaman était connue autrefois sous le nom de *Laranda* (τὰ Λαρανδα). *Λαρανδα* viendrait du louvite *larawanda* ‘les lieux remplis de prospérité’, *arha lara* signifiant ‘prospérer’. M. Forlanini est également partisan de cette hypothèse selon laquelle Landa est la ville de Karaman.” Regarding Landa and *Λαρανδα*, city of Lykaonia (Strabo 12.6.3; KON 330, § 688-1; TIB IV 197-198), M. Forlanini has frequently insisted on a new reading by Popko (1988 92): “Le savant polonais vient de remarquer à propos de KUB LVII 111, que le toponyme lu par l'éditeur Atranta pourrait aussi bien se lire *Laranta* et nous donnerait ainsi la forme hittite du nom de la ville bien connue de *Laranda* (*Laranda*/Karaman)” (1990 120–121). Cf. Forlanini (2013 118 n. 24): “*La-ra-an-ta*, reading suggested by Popko, instead of *At-ra-an-ta* (KUB 57.111 17)” and Forlanini (2017 243 n. 53): “As for the survival of this toponym, both *Leandis* in *Cataonia* and *Laranda* (Karaman) have been proposed (Garstang 1944: 19; Freu 1980: 241). The latter should rather go back to Hittite *Laranda* (KUB 57.111: 17', cf. Popko 1988b: 92).”

kingship of Wiluša⁹⁴ and the existence of a temple of *Kunniyawanni*⁹⁵ in Lanta (“Idaeon”?). Together, these make the interpretation of *Kunilara* — the name of a royal prince⁹⁶ — less arbitrary, and suggest that it may document not merely the onomastic reflex, but the actual presence, in Hatti or the Lower Lands of people and cults originating in northwestern Anatolia.

Abbreviations

ACLT = Annotated Corpus of Luwian Texts.

AHw = Von Soden (1959–1981).

AIO = Attic Inscriptions Online.

AJPh = The American Journal of Philology.

AJA = American Journal of Archaeology.

AnSt = Anatolian Studies.

AoF = Altorientalische Forschungen.

AP = Zgusta (1964a).

ArchOrient = Archív Orientální.

BATL = Talbert (2000).

BCH = Bulletin de Correspondance Hellénique.

BoHa 19 = Herbordt (2005).

BoHa 22 = A. Dinçol and Dinçol (2008).

CAD = Roth et al. (1956–2010).

CHLI = Hawkins (2000).

CIL = Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum.

CLL = Melchert (2001).

CLuw = Cuneiform Luwian.

CMRDM = Lane (1971–1978).

CP = Classical Philology.

DBMAP = Mapping Ancient Polytheisms Database.

DGE = Adrados (1980–).

DGP = Brixhe (1976).

DLL = Melchert (2004).

EA = Epigraphica Anatolica.

eDCo = eDiAna Corpora

[<https://www.ediana.gwi.uni-muenchen.de/corpus.php>].

EDHIL = Kloekhorst (2008).

EDPC 2 = Niehr and Xella (2021).

EGEF = Tsagalis (2017).

FEW = von Wartburg (1934).

GD = Godefroy (1901).

GLyk = Neumann and Tischler (2007).

HED = Puhvel (1984–).

HEG = Tischler (1977–2016).

HF = Zehnder (2010).

HLuw = Hieroglyphic Luwian.

HKM = Alp (1991).

LAMAN = <https://laman.hittites.org/>

IACP = Hansen and Nielsen (2004).

ICilicie = Dagron and Feissel (1987).

⁹⁴ Güterbock (1986 43): “Neither can any of the four equations, Kukkunnis = Kyknos, Alaksandus = Alexandros, Muwatallis = Motylos, and Wilusa = (W)ilios, be proven; there are even some counterindications, as we have seen.” Cf. Neumann (1976); Klengel (1998 146, 151, 193); Beckman (1999 82); Gander (2022 383). Cf. Melchert (2003c 12): “Likewise there is nothing definitively Luwian in the form of the names of the other two known kings of Wilusa, Kukkunni and Walmu (in contrast to those of other western Anatolian kingdoms— see the table in Starke 2001 37).” Bryce (2003 70): “Only three personal names are known to us from Wilusa, two in this treaty. We hear of a predecessor of Alaksandu, a king called Kukkunni, who occupied the vassal throne during the reign of Muwatalli’s grandfather Suppiluliuma. Neither Kukkunni nor Alaksandu is a recognisably Anatolian name, though the first bears a resemblance to Kukkuli (see Güterbock 1986 34).” Hutter (2003 266): “Hans Gustav Güterbock in his very balanced treatment of the possibilities of identifying Wilusa and Troy shows us that the names of famous Wiluseans like Alaksandu and Kukkunni may be either Anatolian or Greek, but there is no recognizable meaning in Luwian for these names (Güterbock 1986 223f).” As for chronology, Bachvarova (2016 xxviii).

⁹⁵ Laroche (1946 84); de Roos (2007 287); Burgin (2022 244). Cf. Forlanini (1998 226 n. 24): “Il teonimo *Kunniyawanni* potrebbe, con qualche difficoltà, essere interpretato come **Ikkuniya-wanni* ed essere inteso come divinità locale di *Ikkuwaniya*, venerata nel vicino e più importante santuario di *Lânda*; più probabile sarebbe però un **Ku(wa)nniya-wanni* che deriverebbe dal toponimo *Kuwanna* o direttamente dal nome del metallo.” Cf. Forlanini (2013 17 n. 71): “a deity exclusively connected to this town was Kunniyawanni, for which I would propose the etymology **Ikkuwaniya-wanni*; this deity would thus be defined by an ethnonym, connecting *Lânda* with the neighbouring *Ikkuwaniya*.” Forlanini (2018 31): “La ville de *Lânda* (*/Layanda/*) apparaît probablement avec *Ušša* dans un inventaire religieux; on y vènerait aussi la divinité *Kunniyawanni*, que pourrait prendre son nom de la ville *Ikkuwaniya* au moyen du suffixe ethnique – *wanni* de la langue louvite.”

⁹⁶ The PN *Kunilara*⁷ on signet 177 bears the two epithets REX.FILIUS and SCRIBA. Cf. Mouton (2006 340): “Un grand nombre de ces sceaux de Nişantepe appartenaient à des princes hittites (REX.INFANS ou de manière plus spécifique REX.FILIUS).”

- IF = Indogermanische Forschungen.
IDidyma = Harder (1958).
IKibyra = Corsten (2002).
IKibyra-Olbasa = Milner (1998).
IManisa = Malay (1994).
ISelge = Nollé and Schindler (1991).
ISultan Dağı I = Jonnes (2002).
IStratonikeia = Şahin (1981).
 JAOS = Journal of the American Oriental Society.
 JCS = Journal of Cuneiform Studies.
 JEOL = Jaarbericht van het Vooraziatisch-Egyptisch Genootschap Ex Oriente Lux.
 JHS = The Journal of Hellenic Studies.
 KAI³ = Donner and Röllig (1971–1976).
 KAI = Donner and Röllig (2002).
 KON = Zgusta (1984).
 KPN = Zgusta (1964b).
 LfgrE = Snell (1955–2010).
 LGPN VA = Corsten, Catling, and Riel (2010).
 LGPN VB = Balzat et al. (2013).
 LGPN VC = Balzat et al. (2018).
 LIV² = Rix et al. (2001).
 LPG = Houwink ten Cate (1961).
 LSJ = Liddell and Scott (1996).
 LW I = Gusmani (1964).
 LW II = Gusmani (1980).
 MAMA IV = Buckler, Calder, and Guthrie (1933).
 MAMA VI = Buckler and Calder (1939).
 MAMA VII = Calder (1956).
 MAMA VIII = Calder et al. (1962).
 MAMA X = Levick et al. (1993).
 MAMA XI = Thonemann, Crowther, and Chiricat (2013).
 McCabe = McCabe (1991).
 MGS = Montanari (2015).
 NABU = Nouvelles Assyriologiques Brèves et Utilitaires.
 NH = Laroche (1966).
 NI = Robert (1963).
 NLH = News from the Lands of the Hittites.
 NP = Melchert (2013).
 Pleiades = *Pleiades: A Gazetteer of Past Places* [https://pleiades.stoa.org].
 RA = Revue archéologique.
 RÉA = Revue des Études Anciennes.
 RÉG = Revue des études grecques.
 RGTC VI = del Monte and Tischler (1978).
 RGTC VII/1 = Bagg (2008).
 RGTC VIII = Zadok (1985).
 RHA = Revue Hittite et Asianique.
 RIMA 3 = Grayson (1996).
 SB = Billerbeck (2006).
 SEG = Supplementum Epigraphicum Graecum.
 SERP = Ramsay (1906).
 SMEA = Studi micenei ed egeo-anatolici.
 SNG = Ritter (1964).
 SNG Arikantürk = Tekin and Erol-Özdizbay (2015–2020).
 StBoTB 4 = Rüster and Wilhelm (2012).
 TAM II = Kalinka (1920–1944).
 TAM III = Heberdey (1941).
 TAM V 1 = Herrmann and Schachermeyr (1981).
 TAM V 3 = Petzl (2007).
 TIB II = Hild and Restle (1981).
 TIB IV = Belke and Restle (1984).
 TIB V = Hild and Hellenkemper (1990).
 TIB VII = Belke and Mersich (1990).
 TIB XIII = Belke (2020).
 T-L = Tobler (1857–2002).
 TL = Kalinka (1901).
 TLL = Thesaurus linguae Latinae.
 TP = Tabula Peutingeriana.
 ZA = Zeitschrift für Assyriologie und vorderasiatische Archäologie.
 ZPE = Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik.

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